

Research Article

Public-Private Sectors' Collaboration in Human Resource Management and Curriculum Development in the Administration of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

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Abstract: The study examined public-private sectors' collaboration in human resource management and curriculum development in the administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The study adopted the descriptive survey design. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study comprised 281 principals in the 281 public secondary schools in Rivers State. The proportionate stratified random sampling technique was used to draw up sample of 259 principals representing 92.2% of the population of the study (211 male principals and 70 female principals). An instrument titled: Public-Private Sectors' Collaboration for School Administration Questionnaire (PPSCSAQ) designed in the modified 4-point Likert Scale with a reliability index of 0.87 was used for data collection. The face and content validities were ensured. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research question while z-test was used in testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The finding of the study showed that to a high extent public-private sectors collaborate in human resource management and curriculum development in the administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. It was recommended among others that the government should provide enabling environment and formulate favourable policies to sustain public-private sectors' collaboration as it ensures effective human resource management in the state.

Keywords: Public-Private Sectors' Collaborations, Human Resource Management, Curriculum Development, Administration and Public Senior Secondary Schools.

Introduction

The administration of public senior secondary schools is critical to the achievement of educational goals in Nigeria. The administration of public senior secondary schools refers to the systematic process of managing public senior secondary school resources, policies and curriculum/programmes for the achievement of predetermined goals of public senior secondary school delivery in Nigeria. According to Edem (2006), public senior secondary school administration is the process of coordinating, directing and harnessing secondary school resources for effective and efficient implementation of senior public secondary school programmes. Administration deals with the deliberate effort to optimizing resource and achieves goals.

Abraham (2003) describes school administration as whatever is done to ensure that predetermined goals of the school are achieved through optimum utilization of available resources. No educational institution can exist without administration. Ikenna (2017) highlights the following as factors that necessitates the practice of administration in the field of education: The time and society are changing, change in institutional facilities, the need to ensure good character development and

efficient utilization of resources. Administration helps to ensure that present and emerging aspirations and challenges of education is catered for in a systematic manner (Egbo and Okeke, 2006). The process of school administration involves resource mobilization, allocation, monitoring and the utilization of resources. The government being the main owner of public senior secondary schools is majorly responsible for its administration. However, the enormous resource requirement for public senior secondary school administration makes the public-private sectors' collaboration imperative.

Public-private sectors' collaboration for public senior secondary school administration involves a joint effort of the public and private sectors to plan, design, finance, implement, monitor and evaluate several public senior secondary school policies and programmes (Ekpeyong, 2016). Public-private sectors' collaboration refers to relationship between the public and private sector that is based on agreed pattern of risk-sharing with reference to the aspirations the public and private sectors in order to foster the achievement of public policy outcome (Jandhyala, 2016). This relationship between the public and private sectors often appears to take the form of long-term (although flexible) contract, for funding of public service (e.g. public secondary school) delivery. Mathonsi (2016) states that public private partnership is any arrangement where the private sector decides to provide various forms of infrastructure (assets) and services for the provision or increase in the access to quality public goods and services that were originally supposed to be provided by the government.

Akintoye *et al.*, (2003) see public-private collaboration as a contractual relationship between government and private sector that is characterized by simultaneous involvement of government and private sector in educational administration. Such contractual relationships appear to be based on market-oriented logic. Mathonsi (2016) notes further that public-private collaboration exists on the basis that there is an unequivocal understanding that the public and collaborating private sectors will share the costs, benefits (risks and rewards). It refers to the situations where the public sector may initiate and commence a programme that will be implemented or monitored by the private sector. It also covers collaboration in areas such as; human resource management, physical facilities management, curriculum development, school business management, financial resource management and research and development (Verger and Moschetti, 2017). This study will however examine public-private sectors' collaboration in human resource management and curriculum development in the administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

School administration cannot be carried out without human resource management. Egbo and Okeke (2006) describe human resources as the totality of persons that are working in an organization. In the field of education, human resource simply refers to the people that are recruited to work in a school. Human resources in public senior secondary schools refer to the teaching and non-teaching staff members that are deployed to implement the curricular and co-curricular programmes and projects in public senior secondary school delivery.

Abraham (2003) sees human resource in education as all the men and women who are members of the school and contribute towards the achievement of the school goals. Stoner *et al.*, (2011) argue that human resource covers the quantity and quality of employees. While the quantity dimension of human resource deals with the size and structure of workforce, the qualitative dimension of human resource refers to the skills, experiences, qualifications, knowledge, talent, and expertise that school staff members possess and which enables them to work productively in school system. Abraham (2003) argues that every resource available to the school should be properly managed.

The process of human resource management is a key issue in school administration. Human resource management refers to the management efforts that are geared towards continuous improvement in the proficiency, morale, commitment and productivity of available human resource. Human resource management also deals with the deliberate efforts towards ensuring that personal needs of staff members are integrated with the goals of the organization. Although it is the responsibility of public

senior secondary school administrators to manage the human resources deployed to their schools. The public and private sectors can collaborate in several ways to enhance the management of human resources in those public senior secondary schools.

Ukoh (2015) surmised that the private sector stakeholders can organize several capacity-building workshops for teachers. The study of Egwu, (2016) on public private partnership for quality assurance in higher education in Imo State found that there is low level of public-private partnership for quality assurance in physical facility and human resource performance in secondary schools. A study on public private partnership and management of higher education in Lagos State, Nigeria by Adelowo (2017) also found that the public-private sector partnership in payment of remuneration and human resource development in public higher education in Lagos State is low.

Curriculum development is another critical element of public senior secondary school administration. Curriculum refers to the totality of experiences given to learners in order to enhance their academic achievement and development. In line with the above view, Mbachu (2012) sees curriculum as the totality of experiences that learners are exposed to from the time they commence a school programme to the time that they complete the school programme. Curriculum involves curricular and co-curricular programmes that are implemented in schools. Curriculum development refers to the process of planning, adopting, implementing and monitoring current and emerging changes in curriculum. Curriculum development refers to the process through which planned changes are made and introduced in the curriculum in order to meet present and future aspirations (Mbachu, 2012).

According to Linus (2017) curriculum development refers to the evolution of curriculum and its impact on the learners and society. The public and private sectors can collaborate to in several ways to ensure smooth, relevant and effective curriculum development in public senior secondary school administration. Although the government appears to be the main actor when it comes to curriculum development in secondary schools, the private sector can also collaborate with the government by initiating some changes in curriculum or by implementing changes made in the curriculum by the government (Dienye, 1995).

Ngeri (2017) in his study on universal basic education curriculum implementation: private sector contributions for quality delivery in ONELGA, Rivers State found that the private sector collaborates with the public sector for curriculum implementation in universal basic education by provision of funds, development of manpower, monitoring and evaluation, research and development as well as supply of physical facilities.

The study of Tamunokuro (2015) on public-private collaboration and quality of public secondary school delivery in Rivers State showed that there is a strong positive relationship between public-private sector collaboration and the quality of curriculum implementation in public secondary school delivery in Rivers State. Based on the above views, the researchers were moved to examine public-private sectors' collaboration in human resource management and curriculum development in the administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

Secondary school administration is a vital mechanism to achieve the predetermined goals of secondary education. Secondary school administration involves several courses of actions that affect every aspect of the life of a school and its outcomes. The government through the Ministry of Education and the Senior Secondary schools Board (SSSB) is responsible for making strategic administrative decisions for the effective operations of public secondary schools. The private sectors might equally perform several complementing roles in the administration of public secondary schools. With their complementary roles quality secondary education could be assured. What however bothered the researchers was that given the alarming quality of the outcome of public secondary school administration in Nigeria and Rivers State in particular, the level of public-private

sectors' collaboration for administration of public secondary schools remains unclear. The question which therefore forms the backdrop of the problem of this study is: What is the extent public-private sectors collaborate for human resource management and curriculum development in the administration of public secondary schools in Rivers state.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study examined public-private sectors' collaboration in human resource management and curriculum development in the administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to achieve the following;

- 1) The extent of public-private sectors' collaboration in human resource management in the administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- 2) The extent of public-private sectors' collaboration in curriculum development in the administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

- 1) To what extent do public-private sectors collaborate in human resource management in the administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
- 2) To what extent do public-private sectors collaborate in curriculum development in the administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypothesis

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- 1) There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the extent public-private sectors collaborate in human resource management in the administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- 2) There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the extent public-private sectors collaborate in curriculum development in the administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Methodology

The study adopted the descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised 281 principals in the 281 public secondary schools in Rivers State. This consisted of 211 male principals and 70 female principals. The proportionate stratified random sampling technique was used to draw up a sample of 259 principals representing 92.2% of the population of the study (203 male principals and 56 female principals) An instrument titled: The Public-Private Sectors' Collaboration for School Administration Questionnaire (PPSCSAQ) designed in the modified 4-point Likert Scale with a reliability index of 0.87 was used for data collection.

Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while z-test was used to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question One

To what extent do public-private sectors collaborate in human resource management in the administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 1. Mean (\bar{x}) and Standard Deviation (SD) on the Responses of Male and Female Principals on the extent Public-Private Sectors collaborate in Human Resource Management in the Administration of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S. No.	Human Resource Management	Male Principals		Female Principals		Total Weighted		Remark
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
1	The Public-private sectors provides training programme for development of personnel employed by the government to work in public secondary schools.	2.90	0.98	3.39	0.91	3.15	0.94	High Extent
2	The Public-private sectors offer incentives for motivating personnel employed by the government to work in public secondary schools.	2.20	1.06	2.36	1.14	2.28	1.10	Low Extent
3	The Public-private sectors provides recruits personnel to work in public secondary schools.	2.90	1.02	3.11	0.97	3.00	0.99	High Extent
4	The Public-private sectors participates in monitoring the performance of personnel employed by the government to work in public secondary schools.	2.80	1.05	3.02	1.00	2.91	1.02	High Extent
5	The Public-private sectors is contracted by the government to carryout recruitment of personnel that will be deployed to work in public secondary schools.	2.69	1.07	3.25	1.00	2.97	1.03	High Extent
6	The Public-private sectors act as resource persons for service delivery in the school.	2.78	1.05	3.07	0.95	2.92	1.00	High Extent
Average		2.71	1.06	3.03	1.04	2.87	1.05	High Extent
Scale: 1.00 – 1.59: Very Low Extent; 1.60 – 2.49: Low Extent; 2.50–3.49: High Extent 3.50–4.00: Very High Extent								

Data on table 1 shows that items 1, 3, 4, 5, and 6 had weighted mean scores between 2.50 and 3.50 which fall under High Extent in the scale of measurement and represents that to a high extent the public and private sectors collaborate in human resources management in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Differently, item 2 had a weighted mean score of 2.28 which falls under 1.60 and 2.49, representing that to a Low Extent, the public and private sectors collaborate in human resource management in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

In summary, with an aggregate weighted mean of 2.87, which fall under 2.50 and 3.50 representing High Extent, the data revealed that public-private sectors to a high extent collaborate in human resource management in the administration of public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question Two

To what extent do public-private sectors collaborate in curriculum development in the administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 2. Mean (\bar{x}) and Standard Deviation (SD) on the Responses of Male and Female Principals on the extent Public-Private Sectors collaborate in Curriculum Development in the Administration of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S. No.	Curriculum Development Variables	Male Principals		Female Principals		Total Weighted		Remark
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
7	The Public-private sectors consults the private sectors before changes are made in secondary school curriculum.	2.89	0.96	3.18	1.01	3.04	0.98	High Extent
8	The Public-private sectors rely on the private sectors for the implementation of changes made in public secondary school curriculum.	2.28	1.05	2.29	1.12	2.28	1.09	Low Extent
9	The Public-private sectors train school personnel for effective implementation of public sectors initiated changes in secondary school curriculum.	3.04	1.02	2.91	1.07	2.98	1.05	High Extent
10	The Public-private sectors donates materials (like textbooks and instructional aid) for the effective curriculum implementation in secondary schools.	2.80	1.01	2.79	1.04	2.79	1.02	High Extent
11	The Public-private sectors monitors the curriculum implementation in public secondary schools.	3.01	0.90	3.21	0.87	3.11	0.88	High Extent
12	The Public-private sectors introduce co-curricular activities in the school.	2.31	1.03	2.34	1.07	2.32	1.05	Low Extent
Average		2.72	1.04	2.79	1.09	2.75	1.06	High Extent

The scale on table 1 applies

Data on table 2 shows that items 7, 9, 10 and 11 had weighted mean scores between 2.50 and 3.50 which fall under High Extent in the scale of measurement and represents that to a high extent the public and private sectors collaborate in curriculum development in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Differently, items 8 and 12 had a weighted mean score of 2.28 and 2.32 respectively which falls under 1.60 and 2.49, representing that to a Low Extent the public and private sectors collaborate in curriculum development in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

In summary, with an aggregate weighted mean of 2.75, which falls under 2.50 and 3.50 representing High Extent, the data indicated that public-private sectors to a high extent collaborate in curriculum development in the administration of public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the extent public-private sectors collaborate in human resource management in the administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 3. Summary of z-test Analysis on the difference between Mean Scores of Male and Female Principals on the extent Public-Private Sectors collaborate in Human Resource Management in the Administration of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Principals	N	\bar{x}	SD	Df	z-cal	z-crit	Sig Level	Decision
Male	203	2.71	1.06	257	2.03	1.96	0.05	Rejected
Female	56	3.03	1.04					

Data on table 3 reveals the summaries of subject, mean, standard deviation and z-test of difference between the means scores of male and female principals on the extent public-private sectors collaborate in human resource management in the administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The calculated z-test value in the test of hypothesis stood at 2.03, while z-critical value stood at 1.96 using 257 degrees of freedom at 0.05 level of significance. At 0.05 level of significance and 257 degrees of freedom, the calculated z-value of 2.03 is greater than the z-critical value of 1.96. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected, and the researchers concluded that there is a significant difference between mean scores of male and female principals on the extent public-private sectors collaborate in human resource management in the administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the extent public-private sectors collaborate) in curriculum development in administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4. Summary of z-test Analysis on the difference between Mean Scores of Male and Female Principals on the extent Public-Private Sectors collaborate in Curriculum Development in the Administration of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Principals	N	\bar{x}	SD	Df	z-cal	z-crit	Sig Level	Decision
Male	203	2.72	1.04	257	0.32	0.752	0.05	Accepted
Female	56	2.79	1.09					

Data on the table 4 shows the summaries of subject, mean, standard deviation and z-test of difference between means scores of male and female principals on the extent public-private sectors collaboration in curriculum development in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The calculated z-test value stood at 0.32, while z-critical value stood at 1.96 using 257 degrees of freedom at 0.05 level of significance. At 0.05 level of significance and 257 degrees of freedom, the calculated z-value of 0.32 is less than the z-critical value of 1.96. Sequel to the above, the null hypothesis was upheld, and the researchers concluded that there is no significant difference between mean scores of male and female principals on the extent public-private sectors collaborate in curriculum development in the administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the study for research question one showed that to a high extent public-private sectors collaborate in human resource management in the administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Furthermore, the test for hypothesis one reveal that there is a significant difference between mean scores of male and female principals on the extent public-private sectors collaborate in human resource management in the administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The finding affirms the position of Ukoh (2015) who surmised that the private sector

stakeholders can organize several capacity-building workshops for teachers. The finding is contrary with Adelowo (2017) who found that the public-private sector partnership in payment of remuneration and human resource development in public higher education in Lagos State is low. The result is equally in contrast with the study of Egwu, (2016) which found that there is low level of public-private partnership for quality assurance in physical facility and human resource performance in secondary schools. This earlier studies demonstrated the weakness of private sectors in collaborating with public (government) sector in managing human resource for administration in schools while the present study shows signs of positive collaboration between the public and private sectors in human resource management in the administration of public senior secondary schools.

The result of the study for research question two revealed that to a high extent public-private sectors collaborate in curriculum development in administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Furthermore, the test for hypothesis revealed that there is no significant difference between mean scores of male and female principals on the extent public-private sectors collaborate in curriculum development in the administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The finding agrees with Nngeri (2017) who found out that the private sector collaborates with the public sector for curriculum implementation in universal basic education by provision of funds, development of manpower, monitoring and evaluation, research and development as well as supply of physical facilities. The result supports the study of Tamunokuro (2015) which showed that there is a strong positive relationship between public-private sector collaboration and the quality of curriculum implementation in public secondary school delivery in Rivers State. This implies that when there are proper collaborations among the public-private sector towards improving its school curriculum, it will go a long way in solving the problems of education and the society at large. Also, since government from inception appears to be the main social unit that is responsible for the management of curriculum development in Nigeria, the private-public collaboration will be able to foster better curriculum development. Moreover, private sectors and groups have the tendency to harness their expertise and resources to improve the quality of learning.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that public-private sectors collaborate in human resource management and curriculum development in the administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher recommended the following;

- 1) The government should provide enabling environment and formulate favourable policies to sustain public-private sectors collaboration to ensure effective human resource management.
- 2) Curriculum developers and planners should always involve private sectors in curriculum development as this would help principals to administer functional secondary education.

Conflicts of interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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